

Synthesis of some New Polycyclic Pyrazolinone Derivatives

M. S. EL-HOSSINI*, A. M. KHALIL**, A. A. EL-AGAMEY and F. Z. EL-ABLAC

Faculty of Science, Damietta, Mansoura University, Egypt

Manuscript received 7 July 1988, revised 27 December 1988, accepted 19 January 1989

Treatment of β -ketoanilides (1a-c) with hydrazine in acetic acid affords the corresponding 6-naphthalinopyrazolinones (2a-c). The synthesis of a series of substituted-naphthalinopyrazolinones is described. Structures of all the compounds were confirmed by elemental analysis, ir and nmr spectral data.

SINCE several reports indicate the pharmacological importance of pyrazolinones, we report here the synthesis of a new series of this class of compounds. Our key intermediates 2a-c were obtained by refluxing the β -ketoanilides (1a-c)¹ with hydrazine hydrate in acetic acid solution containing freshly fused sodium acetate². Structures of these products were based on elemental analysis, ir and nmr spectral data.

Reaction of 2a-c with acetic anhydride³ in presence of fused sodium acetate gave the corresponding acetyl derivatives (3a-c). Also acetylation of 2a-c in dry benzene with chloroacetyl chloride⁴ yielded predominantly the *N*-acylated substances (4a-c) which on reaction with sodium cyanide gave the α -cyanoketo derivatives (5a-c). Treatment of 2a-c with piperidine or morpholine and formaldehyde in acetic acid afforded the *N*-Mannich bases⁴⁻⁶ 6a-c and 7a-c respectively. It seems that the formation of the *N*-Mannich bases involves a base-catalysed addition of 2 to formaldehyde yielding a hydroxymethyl derivative followed by condensation with the secondary amine. In confirmation of the former view, when 2a was refluxed with formaldehyde in acetic acid solution, the hydroxymethyl derivative (8a) was obtained. On warming 8a with piperidine it afforded the corresponding *N*-Mannich base 6a. The formation of 6-8 is in line with that reported⁸ for 4-arylhydrazono-3-methyl-2-pyrazol-5-one.

1,2a : Ar = C₆H₅,
b, Ar = C₆H₄ - OCH₃ - *p*
c, Ar = C₆H₄ - OH₃ - *p*

3a-c, X = COOCH ₃	4a-c, X = COOCH ₂ Cl
5a-c, X = COOCH ₃ ON	6a-c, X = C ₆ H ₅ N
7a-c, X = C ₆ H ₅ NO	8a, X = OH, OH
9a-c, X = OSSH	10a, X = OSNHNH ₂
11a-c, X = Br	12a-c, X = NHNH ₂
13a-c, X = NO	14a-c, X = COOCH ₂ H ₅

15

15a, Ar = C₆H₅
b, Ar = C₆H₄ - OCH₃ - *p*
c, Ar = C₆H₄ - OH₃ - *p*

The hitherto new reaction of 2a-c with carbon disulphide produced the *N*-dithio acid derivatives (9a-c). Reaction of 9a with hydrazine hydrate gave the *N*-thiohydrazide derivative (10a). A selective *N*-bromination of 2a-c using *N*-bromosuccinimide (NBS) in chloroform gave the bromo derivatives (11a-c) which were converted into the *N*-hydrazino derivatives (12a-c) on treatment with hydrazine hydrate. The *N*-nitroso compounds (13a-c) were also obtained on treatment of 2a-c with sodium nitrate and acetic acid. The pyrazolinones (2a, c) were reacted with ethyl chloroformate in benzene to yield the *N*-carbethoxy derivatives (14a, c).

In contrast to the action of acetic anhydride or chloroacetyl chloride on 2a-c, when the latter were heated with benzene sulphonyl chloride in presence of pyridine, 15a-c were obtained as inferred from its ir spectra which do not reveal any carbonyl absorption bands. Similar behaviour has been reported⁷ for the reaction of 3-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-5-one and 5-methyl-1-phenyl-2-pyrazolin-3-one (Table 1).

Experimental

Elemental analysis was performed in the Micro-analytical Unit, Mansoura University. Infrared spectra were recorded on a Pye-Unicam SP 1200 spectrophotometer. Melting points are uncorrected.

1-Arylidene-5,7-diaryl-1,2,3,4,4a,5,5a,7-octahydro-naphthalenopyrazol-(6H)-6-one (2a-c): A mixture

*Faculty of Science, Mansoura, Mansoura University, Egypt.

TABLE 1—PHYSICAL DATA OF COMPOUNDS*

Compd. no.	M.p. °C	Yield %	Mol. formula
2a	288	75	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ N ₂ O
2b	275	70	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂
2c	280	80	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₂ O
3a	205	80	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₂
3b	160	75	C ₂₉ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₄
3c	195	82	C ₂₉ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₂
4a	192	80	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂ Cl
4b	165	75	C ₂₈ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₄ Cl
4c	170	82	C ₂₉ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₂ Cl
5a	295	70	C ₂₇ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂
5c	182	70	C ₂₉ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₂
6a	202	80	C ₃₀ H ₂₈ N ₂ O
6b	230	73	C ₃₂ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₂
6c	242	80	C ₃₂ H ₂₇ N ₂ O
7a	208	75	C ₂₉ H ₂₇ N ₂ O ₂
7b	215	72	C ₃₁ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₄
7c	238	75	C ₃₁ H ₂₈ N ₂ O ₂
9a	110	60	C ₂₅ H ₂₂ N ₂ OS ₂
9b	119	72	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ S ₂
9c	115	80	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ N ₂ OS ₂
11a	> 300	72	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ N ₂ OBr
11b	> 300	70	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ N ₂ O ₂ Br
11c	299	71	C ₂₆ H ₂₅ N ₂ OBr
12a	> 300	70	C ₂₄ H ₂₄ N ₂ O
12b	> 300	75	C ₂₆ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂
12c	> 300	60	C ₂₆ H ₂₈ N ₂ O
13a	205	80	C ₂₈ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂
13b	200	85	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₄
13c	210	59	C ₂₈ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂
14a	256	50	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂
14c	200	49	C ₂₉ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂
15a	210	80	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂ S
15b	120	70	C ₃₂ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₂ S
15c	145	70	C ₃₂ H ₃₀ N ₂ O ₂ S

*All compounds gave satisfactory C and H analyses.

of 1a-c (0.01 mol) and hydrazine in glacial acetic acid (50 ml) was refluxed for 4 h. The solid product that separated on cooling was filtered and crystallised from ethanol to give 2a-c as white crystals; ν_{\max} (KBr) 3 300 (NH), 1 710 (C=O) and 1 610 cm⁻¹ (C=N); 2a δ 7.6-7.1 (10H, m, Ar), 6.8 (1H, s, =CH), 6.0 (1H, s, NH) and 3.1-1.0 (6H, m, aliphatic).

5-Aryl-1-arylidene-7-acetyl-1,2,3,4,4a,5,5a,7-octahydronaphthalenopyrazol-(6H)-one (3a-c): A suspension of 2a-c (0.01 mol) and freshly fused sodium acetate (0.01 mol) in acetic anhydride (30 ml) was refluxed for 6 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled and poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give 3a-c; ν_{\max} (KBr) 1 720 (CO-CH₃), 1 640 (CONH), 1 610 cm⁻¹ (C=N); 3a δ 7.7-7.2 (10H, m, Ar), 6.8 (1H, s, =CH), 3.1-1.1 (6H, m, aliphatic), 1.9 (3H, s, COCH₃).

5-Aryl-1-arylidene-7-chloroacetyl-1,2,3,4,4a,5,5a,7-octahydronaphthalenopyrazol-(6H)-6-one (4a-c): To a mixture of 2a-c (0.01 mol) and chloroacetyl chloride (0.03 mol), a few drops of pyridine were added. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a steam-bath for 2 h and left overnight at room temperature. The resulting solid was filtered and crystallised from the appropriate solvent to give the chloroacetyl derivatives (4a-c); ν_{\max} (KBr)

1 700 (CO-CH₂Cl), 1 650 (CO-N=) and 1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N); 4a δ 7.5-7.0 (10H, m, Ar), 6.9 (1H, s, =CH), 3.5 (2H, m, CH₂) and 3.1-1.0 (6H, m, aliphatic).

5-Aryl-1-arylidene-7-cyanoacetyl-1,2,3,4,4a,5,5a,7-octahydronaphthalenopyrazol-(6H)-6-one (5a, c): Compounds 4a, c (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) were treated with an equimolecular amount of sodium cyanide (0.01 mol) dissolved in water (3 ml). The mixture was refluxed for 0.5 h and then cooled to room temperature. The separated sodium chloride was filtered off and the filtrate was evaporated under reduced pressure to give an oily residue which solidified on washing with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) and was crystallised from benzene to give the α -cyanoketo derivatives (5a, c); ν_{\max} (KBr) 2 220 (C=N), 1 710 (C=O) and 1 610 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

5-Aryl-1-arylidino-7-(piperidino or morpholino methyl)-1,2,3,4,4a,5,5a,7-octahydronaphthalenopyrazol-(6H)-6-one (6a-c or 7a-c): General procedure: In an ice-bath, a mixture of the appropriate secondary amine (0.01 mol), cold acetic acid (30 ml) and aqueous formaldehyde (2.5 ml, 35%) were added to 2a-c (0.01 mol). The mixture was allowed to warm up to room temperature with occasional shaking until the mixture become clear. The solution was kept at room temperature overnight, then poured with vigorous stirring into a solution of potassium hydroxide and cooled in an ice-bath for 2 h. The resulting solid was filtered, washed with cold water and crystallised from ethanol to give the corresponding N-Mannich bases (6 and 7); ν_{\max} (KBr); 2 925 (NH), 1 680 (CON=) and 1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

5-Aryl-1-arylidene-7-hydroxymethyl-1,2,3,4,4a,5,5a,7-octahydronaphthalenopyrazol-(6H)-6-one (8a): To a suspension of 2a (0.01 mol) in acetic acid (30 ml), aqueous formaldehyde (35%; 10 ml) was added. The reaction mixture was refluxed for 3 h and the solvent removed under reduced pressure. The oily product was allowed to solidify on standing overnight and then crystallised from ethanol to give the hydroxymethyl derivative (8a) as a cream powder (63%), m.p. 270° (Found: C, 78.26; H, 6.14. C₂₈H₂₄N₂O₂ calcd. for: C, 78.13; H, 6.25%); ν_{\max} 3 400 (OH), 1 650 (CON=) and 1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N); δ 7.5-7.2 (10H, m, Ar), 4.4 (2H, m, CH₂), 3.4 (1H, s, OH) and 3.1-1.1 (6H, m, aliphatic).

5-Aryl-1-arylidene-7-dithioacid-1,2,3,4,4a,5,5a,7-octahydronaphthalenopyrazol-(6H)-6-one (9a-c): The pyrazolone derivative (2a-c; 0.01 mol) was added to an excess amount of dry carbon disulphide and a few drops of pyridine. The resulting clear solution was kept at 0° for 48 h. The reaction mixture was then evaporated under reduced pressure and the solid obtained was crystallised from benzene to give 9a-c as yellow crystals; ν_{\max} (KBr) 2 570 (SH), 1 650 (C=O), 1 620 (C=N) and 2 140 cm⁻¹ (C=S); 9a δ 7.5-7.1 (10H, m, Ar), 6.9 (1H, s, =CH), 5.1 (1H, s, SH) and 3.0-1.1 (6H, m, aliphatic).

5-Aryl-1-arylidene-7-thiohydrazide-1,2,3,4,4a,5,5a,7-octahydronaphthalenopyrazol-(6H)-6-one (10a) : A mixture of **9a** (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (98% ; 0.012 mol) in absolute ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed until hydrogen sulphide evolution ceased (3 h). The reaction mixture was then filtered while hot and the filtrate concentrated under reduced pressure. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give **10a** as white crystals, m.p. 140 (Found : C, 69.82 ; H, 5.37. $C_{25}H_{24}N_4OS$ calcd. for : C, 70.09 ; H, 5.61%) ; ν_{max} 3450, 3250 (NHNH₂), 1640 (CO), 1620 (C=N) and 1140 cm^{-1} (C=S) ; δ 7.5–7.1 (10H, m, Ar), 7.0 (1H, s, =CH), 6.5 (1H, s, NH), 4.6 (2H, s, NH₂) and 3.1–1.0 (6H, m, aliphatic).

5-Aryl-1-arylidene-7-bromo-1,2,3,4,4a,5,5a,7-octahydronaphthalenopyrazol-(6H)-6-one (11a-c) : An equimolar (0.01 mol) mixture of **2a-c** and *N*-bromosuccinimide in chloroform (30 ml) was stirred in direct sunlight for 2 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give **11a-c** ; ν_{max} 1690 (CO), 1650 (C=N) and 730 cm^{-1} (NBr) ; **11a** δ 7.6–7.2 (10H, m, Ar), 7.1 (1H, s, =CH) and 3.3–1.0 (6H, m, aliphatic).

5-Aryl-1-arylidene-7-hydrazine-1,2,3,4,4a,5,5a,7-octahydronaphthalenopyrazol-(6H)-6-one (12a-c) : A mixture of **2a-c** (0.01 mol) and hydrazine hydrate (0.01 mol) in ethanol (30 ml) was refluxed for 0.5 h. The solution was then cooled and the resulting solid was washed with dilute ammonia, air-dried and crystallised from ethanol to give **12a-c** as green crystals ; ν_{max} 3420–3230 (NH, NH₂), 1690 (CO) and 1650 cm^{-1} (C=N) ; **12a** δ 7.7–7.1 (10H, m, Ar), 7.0 (1H, s, =CH), 6.4 (1H, s, NH), 4.5 (2H, s, NH₂) and 3.1–1.0 (6H, m, aliphatic).

5-Aryl-1-arylidene-7-nitroso-1,2,3,4,4a,5,5a,7-octahydronaphthalenopyrazol-(6H)-6-one (13a-c) : A solution of **2a-c** (0.01 mol) in acetic acid (20 ml) was treated at 3° with a cold concentrated solution of sodium nitrite (0.02 mol). The mixture was

stirred while cold for 1 h and left overnight in the refrigerator. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give **13a-c** ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1700 (C=O), 1640 (C=N) and 1590 cm^{-1} (N=O) ; **13a** δ 7.7–7.1 (10H, m, Ar), 7.0 (1H, s, =CH) and 3.1–1.1 (6H, m, aliphatic).

5-Aryl-1-arylidene-7-carbethoxy-1,2,3,4,4a,5,5a,7-octahydronaphthalenopyrazol-(6H)-6-one (14a-c) : Ethyl chloroformate (0.01 mol) in cold dry benzene (20 ml) was added dropwise with stirring to a solution of **2a, c** (0.01 mol) in DMF (20 ml). The mixture was kept at 0° for 24 h. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give **14a, c** as cream crystals ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1720 (C=O) and 1630 cm^{-1} (C=N) ; **14a** δ 7.5–7.1 (10H, m, Ar), 7.0 (1H, s, =CH), 4.3 (2H, q, CH₂) and 3.1–1.0 (9H, m, aliphatic + CH₃).

5-Aryl-1-arylidene-1,2,3,4,4a,5,5a-heptahydronaphthalenopyrazol-6-yl-benzenesulphonate (15a-c) : To a suspension of **2a-c** (0.01 mol) in pyridine (15 ml), benzene sulphonylchloride (0.01 mol) was added and the mixture was refluxed for 6 h, set aside at room temperature for several hours, and then poured into ice-cold water. The resulting solid was crystallised from ethanol to give **15a-c** as brown crystals ; ν_{max} (KBr) 1620 cm^{-1} (C=N) ; no carbonyl group appeared.

References

1. M. S. EL-HOSSINI, A. M. KHALIL, A. I. OSMAN and F. Z. EL-ABLAC, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, in the communicated.
2. C. G. BARETT, M. M. EL-ABADIAH and M. HERGRAVES, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1970, 1986.
3. A. HAREHASH, A. F. AMER and M. A. METWALLEY, *Mansoura Sci. Bull.*, 1976, 4, 223.
4. F. F. BLICKE, "Organic Reactions", 1942, Vol. 1, Chap. 10.
5. J. N. COCKER and M. FIELDS, *J. Org. Chem.*, 1962, 27, 2226.
6. C. MANNICH and W. KROSCHKE, *Arch. Pharm.*, 1912, 250 647.
7. A. A. GALOYAN, S. G. AGHALYAN and G. T. ESAYAN, *Chem. Abstr.*, 1969, 71, 70585.